

**CONTEMPORARY UNDERSTANDING OF YONIVYAPAD (GYNECOLOGICAL
DISORDERS) THROUGH AYURVEDIC AND MODERN ASPECT**¹*Dr. Madhavi R. Khuje, ²Dr. Prerana P. Raut¹M.D. Rognidan, Associate Professor – Vilasrao Deshmukh Ayurvedic College and Research Center, Mouda, Nagpur.²M.D. Rognidan, Assistant Professor – R.R. Kambe Ayurvedic College, Murtijapur.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Madhavi R. Khuje**M.D. Rognidan, Associate Professor - Vilasrao Deshmukh Ayurvedic College and Research Center, Mouda, Nagpur. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19327212>**How to cite this Article:** ¹*Dr. Madhavi R. Khuje, ²Dr. Prerana P. Raut. (2026). Contemporary Understanding Of Yonivyapad (Gynecological Disorders) Through Ayurvedic And Modern Aspect. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(4), 13–15.

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ABSTRACT

Yonivyapad is classical *Ayurvedic* gynecological concept describing disorders of the female reproductive tract i.e. vagina, cervix, uterus; caused mainly by *dosha* imbalance i.e. *dosha vaigunya*, improper hygiene, infection, trauma or inappropriate lifestyle. Around 20 types of *Yonivyapad* are elaborated in *Ayurvedic samhitas* with its treatment. Thus article review the concept of *yonivyapad*, its classification, clinical presentation and management along with this most importantly contemporary etiological factors of *Yonivyapad* which will help in prevention of disease and its early management.

KEYWORDS: *Yonivyapad*, Ayurvedic gynecological disorders, *Nidan panchak*.**INTRODUCTION**

In *Ayurveda*, the female reproductive system is given prime importance due to its role in reproduction and maintenance of health. The term *yon* refers to the entire female genital tract, while *vyapad* denotes disease or disorder. *Yonivyapad* thus encompasses a wide spectrum of gynecological ailments.

Ancient *Acharyas* like *Charak*, *Sushrut*, *Waghata* have described *Yonivyapad* in detail, emphasizing *dosha* involvement, lifestyle factors and therapeutic measure.

In contemporary gynecology, disorders of the female reproductive tract constitute a major public health concern due to their high prevalence, recurrent nature and impact on reproductive and psychological health. Modern medicine classifies gynecological disorders based on microbial etiology, hormonal imbalance, inflammatory pathology and structural abnormalities. Conditions such as vaginitis, cervicitis, pelvic inflammatory disease, dysfunctional uterine bleeding and atrophic vaginitis show close resemblance to various types of *Yonivyapad*.

Lifestyle changes in the modern era, such as sedentary habits, altered dietary patterns, stress, excessive use of

antibiotics and poor menstrual hygiene have significantly contributed to the increasing incidence of gynecological disorders. These factors align with *Ayurvedic nidanas* like *mithya ahar vihar*, *vegadharana* and *manasika bhavas* leading to *doshas prakopa* and *artavavaha srotodushti*.

Diagnostic modalities in modern gynecology such as per speculum examination, vaginal swab analysis, Pap smear and USG complement Ayurvedic diagnostic principles based on lakshanas, *dosha* assessment and *samprapti vighatana*. An integrative diagnostic approach enhances early detection and accurate classification of disease.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

To understand the contemporary aspect of *Yonivyapad* (Gynecological disorders) through *Ayurvedic* and modern view.

Material**Review of literature**

1. Literature regarding *yonivyapad* was studied from classical *Ayurvedic* text books.
2. Literatures regarding gynecological disorders were studied from modern text books.
3. Internet data were studied.

DISCUSSION

Nidan

According to Ayurvedic literature, *Nidan* of *Yonivyapad* include,

1. *Mihtya ahar vihar* (improper diet and lifestyle)
2. *Vega dharan* (suppression of natural urges)
3. *Ativyavay* (Excessive coitus or improper sexual practices)
4. *Asuchi* (Poor genital hygiene)
5. *Atichinta* (Psychological stress)
6. *Aghat* (Trauma to reproductive organs)

These factors vitiate *vata*, *pitta*, *kapha doshas*, leading to various *Yonivyapad* conditions.

Contemporary etiological factors

In this Contemporary era, lifestyle changes have increased the prevalence of *Yonivyapad*. These are as follows,

- Sedentary lifestyle and obesity
- Poor menstrual hygiene
- Recurrent antibiotic use altering vaginal flora
- Stress and hormonal imbalance
- Unsafe sexual practices
- Environmental toxins
- Endocrine disruptors
- Eating unhealthy and junk food

Samprapti – (pathogenesis)

Vitiated *doshas* localize in the *yonni* due to *khavaigunya* (favourable condition for *dosha vaigunya*) affecting *Artav*, *Rasa*, *Rakta* and *Mamsa dhatus*. Predominance of *vata* causes pain and dryness. *Pitta* leads to inflammation and vaginal discharge while *kapha* causes itching and excessive secretions. Long lasting complaints may lead to complications such as infertility, PCOS, CA of uterus, cervix etc.

Flow chart of pathogenesis of *Yonivyapad* –

Classification - it is done on the basis of *doshik* predominance.

According to *Acharya Charaka*, *Sushrut* and *Wagbhata* – 20 types.

Vataja Yonivyapad

1. *Vataja* – It is characterized by pain, dryness, constriction, twitching at the site of *yonni* (female reproductive system).
2. *Vandhya* - Absence of menstruation during puberty results in failure to conceive. It has two subtypes – 1. *Adivandhya* – primary infertility 2. *Anapatya* – secondary infertility
3. *Udavarta* – it is characterized by severe pain before menstruation delayed or obstructed flow, relief of pain after menstruation, flatulence, constipation, irritability, anxiety. This occurs due to the upward movement of *vata*.
4. *Vipluta* – it is characterized by severe throbbing pain, burning sensation and inflammation of genital tract due to excessive sexual intercourse.
5. *Paripluta* – it is characterized by tenderness, inflammation, burning sensation at the site of *yonni*. Symptoms get aggravated during intercourse and results in painful intercourse.

Pittaja Yonivyapad

1. *Pittaja* - it is characterized by severe burning sensation in *yonni*, pain, yellow or green discharge, inflammation, tenderness, mild fever.
2. *Putraghni* - In this repeated abortions seen, inability to maintain pregnancy, lower abdominal pain, irregular menstruation.
3. *Vamini* – *Shukra vaman* i.e. expulsion of semen immediately after intercourse, infertility, pain in lower abdomen, reduced sexual satisfaction.
4. *Prasamsinee* - Displacement or prolapse of *yonni* or *garbhashaya*, heaviness in pelvis, pain in lower abdomen and back.
5. *Lohitakshara* – excessive bleeding from the *yonni*, burning sensation, pain in lower abdomen, excessive thirst, giddiness and weakness due to blood loss.

Kaphaja Yonivyapad

1. *Kaphaja* – white, thick, sticky discharge, no or little pain, itching, heaviness in pelvic region, mild foul smell. These symptoms seen in *Kaphaj Yonivyapad*.
2. *Karnini* - it is characterized by the formation of *granthi* like fleshy growth in the *yonni* which looks like the shape of an ear hence known as *karnini*. Pain and occasional bleeding at the site of *granthi*. Dyspareunia also seen in this condition.
3. *Acharana* – in this, the women deliberately avoids sexual intercourse due to pain and discomfort.
4. *Aticharana* - in this, women desire for excessive sexual activity, burning and pain in *yonni*, general weakness.
5. *Ayananda* – excessive desire for intercourse, repeated urge even after coitus, minimal or no pain.

Sannipataja Yonivyapad

1. *Sarvaja* – caused by vitiation of *vata pitta* and *kapha dosha*. It presents with mixed clinical features and it is difficult to treat. Pain, burning sensation, thick

foul discharge, bleeding, itching, swelling, painful coitus these symptoms seen in this condition.

2. *Falini* - menstruation is regular, normal sexual activity but failure to conceive despite repeated attempts, no major structural abnormality.
3. *Mahayoni* - wide vaginal passage, reduced sexual satisfaction, pain in yoni, vaginal discharge
4. *Suchivaktra* - extremely narrow vaginal orifice, severe dyspareunia, dryness of yoni, menstruation may or may not be normal.
5. *Shandi* – woman who lacks sexual desire and feminine sexual characteristics resembling a *shand* means impotent. It is due to defective *shukra* and *artav*. Absent or very low sexual desire, poorly developed secondary sexual characters, scanty or absent menstruation, dyspareunia, infertility.

Modern correlation

Kaphaj Yonivyapad – Vaginal candidiasis

Pittaj Yonivyapad – Cervicitis, vaginitis

Vataja Yonivyapad – Atrophic vaginitis

Raktayoni – Dysfunctional uterine bleeding

CONCLUSION

Thus the contemporary relevance of *Yonivyapad* lies in its holistic, preventive and individualized approach. Correlating classical *Ayurvedic* concepts with modern gynecological science not only validates the traditional knowledge system but also opens avenues for integrative women centered healthcare.

Ayurvedic management of *Yonivyapad* emphasizes *nidan parivarjanam*, *shodhan*, *shaman*, and *sthanik chikitsa* such as *yoniprakshalana*, *yonipichu* aiming at root cause correction and restoring of physiological balance.

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